

6. The 'energetic symmetry' that infuses our Universe indicates the potential we humans have to create a remedial process that can address the dis-ease of radiation that afflicts the fissioned particles.

In contrast to the White-man's technology which works to 'split the atom', African society looks capable of developing a collective spiritual process able to 'heal the atom'.

I prepared this 'five part paper' to highlight the "energetic symmetry" that is evident at every level of our Universe. This profound understanding comes from viewing the heavens above and the atoms below with what I think of as an "African consciousness". This approach sees the experiential nature of phenomena which then complements the objective knowledge that the Western mind excels at collecting. My sense is that by combining the knowledge that comes from looking both way, we begin to see the universal nature of our Universe.

This whole understanding found a home in me as a consequence of my childhood in Kenya where I was influenced on the one hand by my British parents, and on the other by simply living simply amongst African people in a landscape barely touched by modernity. I am far from being the first to observe this principle of universal symmetry. The civilisations of Ancient Egypt saw it for themselves, and described the whole effect with the simple phrase ... **"As above, so below"**.

In our time, this same concept of universal symmetry is becoming known as the **"holographic nature of our Universe"**.

The Christian view of this principle finds expression in the statement Christ made to his followers when he said: **"In my Father's house are many rooms,"**

In my understanding, He was implying that we humans live in just this one room, this one dimension of our Universe. But the time will come when we will realise there are many dimensions, many rooms, to the whole universal system that we are within. We are familiar already with the 'room' above us, being as the home of the Moon and the Sun, while the room below and inside of where and who we are, is the Atomic realm, home for the particle population.

Black and white observations tell us that the same 'four kinds of energy' are in each room. Three of these are forms of Love, while the fourth is a form of Light.

This children's ditty casually describes the very same principle:

**Big fleas have little fleas, upon their backs to bite 'em.
And little fleas have lesser fleas, and so ... ad infinitum.**

The series of internally-stacking **Russian Dolls** provides an excellent example of an 'holographic system'. As do our own personal families, with each generation nestled inside of the preceding one.

The knowledge needs to go round, of the atomic particles being social and sentient, the same as us humans. The sentience of the atomic particles can really only be known by getting out of our safety mentality and experiencing the feeling of what nuclear radiation feels like. Then we'll get some idea of the suffering of the fissioned particles. Radioactivity is measure of their despair and sadness.

I can write like this only because I worked at a nuclear reactor and found a place where I could experience the extraordinary distress emanating from spent fuel rods. This discharge of negative emotions suggests to me that the fissioned particles will be hugely receptive to the experience of being loved, of being at the receiving end of a collective expression of Love and warm thoughts from a group of women and men, seeking to combine these forces that live within us.

galactic magnitude

sun, moon, earth system

human family

particle families

This is family work. But now at a scale we have not explored so far. Nonetheless, Humanity has an instinct for working together to nurture our children's world, along with the animals and plants whom we have domesticated, who move in with us because they like the experience of being cared for and loved, even if it is imperfectly done. No one else gives it to them.

In this mood, I think the stage is set for us humans to experiment and develop group processes whereby we might seek to create quantum units of the two fundamental forces, 'feminine power' and 'masculine strength', that one way or another have a home in all of us. The same qualities as are in the light of the Moon and the light of the Sun. The same as they are in the neutrons and protons who together form the nucleus of 'atoms'. In metaphysical terms, we'll be learning to make 'photons', to convey what are in effect units of our universal energy, to land in the next level down from where we are. In this context, the atomic particles are as the children of our Universe. This understanding signifies how we humans, we Humanity, need to work collectively to be as effective parents or god-parents for the particle world.

I sense we are on watch, on duty for the well-being of the whole Atomic realm, the same as the Moon and the Sun are on watch and committed to care for the Earth and us earthlings, and everything that lives here. We are part of a long series of family systems which we can not really know how or where it all began, and how it might go on. Was the Big Bang formative. Our Western mind gravitates to this idea. Are the atomic particles responsible for the well-being of the dimension downstairs and inside of where they are? It feels very possible. If we align with this whole picture, I feel we will be going in the right direction. Right for us, with room for future generations to see if it works for them.

I am moved by experience to believe that singing together is the engine room for this venture to 'heal the atom'. I'll leave the idea there, without much more direction than recounting how I have attended and participated in collective celebrations and devotions and religious practice(s) in East and South Africa. The experiences incline me to say how African people have an instinct for collective work which I see as essential for developing an healing process for the dis-ease we know as radioactivity. If we can reach down into the Atomic realm with our home-made photons, and top up or wash down the radioactive particles with units of our Love and Light, then I think we will be opening a door to the future.

I think already that the nuclear nations will be glad to know that this kind of work is being considered. If it is successful, then we have a social technology able to address the issues of the radioactive waste materials accumulating alongside each reactor. The funds being set aside to pay for the underground repositories that each nation plans to develop would surely be due any group or national body who has an aptitude for an healing approach to the radioactive materials.

Dear Women, the whole nuclear subject especially needs your interest and involvement. The Atomic World, viewed with a feminine gaze, feels to be more social and sentient than we have so far cared or dared to consider. Matriarchal experience and acumen helps us realise the whole social nature of this next-floor-down realm with its vast population of family systems. They are as busy as we are with relationships, with the demands of family life, with raising their electron children while interacting positively with their neighbours and neighbourhood.

Becoming a parent myself, being in a steady relationship with a steadfast woman, raising children together, registering the pre-conceptual views of the children themselves, all of this helped me enormously to realise the family processes going on in the Atomic World.

Now we clever men have developed the fission process, which works for us by breaking up the large community-like atoms that form the element Uranium. Fission causes the four kinds of energy that are at work and play between the particles in each atom, to come free and be available for our use.

Your moonlight and tenderness, your electromagnetic field, is balm for wounded and hurting people. It will surely be the same for the radioactive particles. Only that the atomic particles are in effect as small to us humans as we are small to the Sun, that we need to work out how to amplify and focus y/our power (says the man in me), that 'she' can be felt down in the landscape where they are. Yet I sense that the substantial change of magnitude between the dimension that we humans live within and the atomic dimension means that we will have quite some leverage in our favour, if and when we engage with them. We men can hold the door, warm the room, whatever is required to help your tribe gather and work together. Healing the atom, addressing the dis-ease and distress of the particle population, looks to be an attribute of your whole nature.

I have the idea that a common household smoke detector, devices that are powered by a tiny chip of Americium 141 (a radioactive isotope created in a nuclear reactor) can serve as a monitor for this civilian adventure, that can quickly learn if the 'photons' that we might create and direct to land amongst the radioactive particles, are affective in alleviating their distress.

A radioactive chip is used in this device because the negative ions that the chip emits are used to create a small electric current that tests - as it jumps an air-gap - if smoke particles are in the air. If they are, the flow of ions is blocked, and the electric current ceases. At which point the device is programmed to sound its alarm.

My thinking is that if the group's singing can land a photon pulsating with Love and Light amongst the radioactive particles, might this cause the radioactive particles to cease discharging their negative emotions, if only for a nanosecond. That would be enough to stop the electric current, at which point the alarm would sound. In effect signalling - thank you for your love and concern. We feel it and relax, feel better and cease emitting our signal of distress.

I can imagine there are more sophisticated or perhaps simpler ways to determine if we can ameliorate the distress of radioactive particles. May they all succeed, and us too, in exploring how we might communicate with the particle world.

Closing thoughts.

The insight that came from my childhood in northern Kenya, of seeing on many occasions how the Moon and the Sun are the same apparent size, this helped me to see how there is an inside and outside way of viewing our planetary system, and both are good. This realisation prepared me to look down into the particle world and see how the atomic particles are social and sentient, the same as ourselves.

Observing the wholeness and holiness of the heavenly Light that we are within, prepares us to see the Atomic World in the same way. We can not forego or forget our nuclear knowledge. There is no going back. The only way out then is to go in deeper. Look with more care. Care more about how we look. Observe the family nature of this dynamic multi-tiered universal system we are within and recognise our ability to work together and develop a positive and loving relationship and approach to the particle population. Metaphorically, they are as the children of our Universe.

If a collective spiritual approach to the particle realm proves able to ameliorate the phenomena of radiation, then we will have a social technology in our back pocket that can be brought in the first instance to address the fairly substantial radioactive waste issues that our abundant use of nuclear reactors has created. This same healing process could in turn be used to stabilise the unstable elements, typically enriched uranium and plutonium, which would then make nuclear weapons vulnerable and mutable, more than has so far been anticipated.

As with begetting children, our awareness and concern for the Atomic World will be with us and part of our human story, now and forever more. This means we have long term duties of care and responsibility for the particle world that will need to be part of daily life. Our responsibilities are expanding. How else can it be when we live in an expanding and symmetrical Universe. The future looks remarkably adventurous, with our quest to explore the outer Universe matched by the need to look inwards and know our own universal nature. The one nourishing the other. Now, good wishes for the shared dreaming and work that can take us into the future.

Asante, nimefurahi kukutana nawe.
Mambo yote yaende sawa kwako na kwa watu wako.

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